

FAST CURES FOR THICK LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A quick cure schedule was developed for a one inch thick laminated graphite/epoxy composite. The heatup time required to reach the epoxy reaction temperature was reduced to 60 minutes from in excess of 300 minutes. A numerical optimization scheme based on a process model that accounted for the type of tooling was used to calculate the time-optimal cure schedule. The model was shown to accurately predict the unsteady temperature distribution through the thickness during cure. The physical constraints of the processing equipment such as maximum heating and cooling rates and maximum and minimum temperatures were included in the optimization scheme. A Crank-Nicolson type finite difference scheme that employed an iterative calculation at each time step was found to be only slightly more accurate than a similar scheme in which the iterative calculation was not done.

BACKGROUND

Cure schedules used to process prepreg ensure that the solid laminate exhibits certain required chemical, physical and mechanical properties. The standard and accepted cure is accomplished by heating the prepreg from room temperature to reaction temperature 177°C at rates ranging from $.56\text{--}5.6^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, holding at 177°C for about 120 min, and then cooling at rates between $.56\text{--}5.6^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Deviations from the cure schedule can compromise the integrity of the laminate. This processing window was developed for thin laminates, less than about 1.9 cm thick.

Severe problems can be experienced when processing laminates thicker than about 2.54 cm if the laminate temperature is not controlled properly. If the exothermic heat of reaction is not dissipated for example, it heats the prepreg which causes the epoxy to react faster. This further increases the prepreg temperature which in turn causes the epoxy to react even faster. A runaway reaction results and the prepreg quickly heats to very high temperatures.

The materials studied was IM6/3501-6 a commercial graphite/epoxy prepreg available from Hercules Inc. It is widely used throughout the aerospace industry and typical of the graphite/epoxy type prepreps.

The work presented in this paper outlines the development of a one dimensional mathematical model of the unsteady temperature distribution in the prepreg during cure. The type of tooling used to process the prepreg was accounted for. A Crank-Nicolson type finite difference scheme was used to transform the governing set of partial differential equations into a set of non-linear algebraic equations. An iterative approach making use of the Taylor series for functions of several variables was used to solve the algebraic equations. An optimization scheme that minimized the heatup time was developed. The function minimized was defined as the absolute value of the difference between a prescribed temperature profile and the calculated profile. A penalty was associated with temperature excursions above 182°C . The error in those cases was defined as two times the absolute value of the difference. Processing constraints such as maximum and

minimum temperatures and maximum heating and cooling rates were included.

RESULTS

A cross-sectional view through the thickness of the tooling setup is shown in Figure 1. Two laminates were cured to verify the accuracy of the process model. Both laminates were 128 plies thick which corresponds to 2.49 cm. The tool plate and caul were 1.27 cm thick glass/silicone laminates. The results are shown in Figures 2 and 3. Both laminates failed to pass the materials specification regarding cure. The results of testing the model against published data is given in Figure 4. The same material was used but in this case the laminate stack was 3.8 cm thick. The laminate passes materials specification however, 300 minutes was required to reach reaction temperature.

The goal of optimization is to cure the laminate in the shortest possible time, while keeping it within certain materials specifications regarding heatup rate and cure temperature. The optimization strategy is to make the thick laminate experience the same type of cure as does a thin one. This requires operating the autoclave in new ways, but a thermocouple buried in the laminate would indicate temperature readings identical to those of a thin laminate cured in the usual manner.

The first step in the development is to choose a typical temperature profile associated with a thin laminate. Next, for the thick laminate, determine how to operate the autoclave so that the laminate midpoint temperature matches that of the thin laminate. This is done with the heat of reaction set equal to zero. This is a relatively simple task. The profile so determined becomes the target defined as the best possible one.

An error function, defined as the absolute value of the difference between the target profile and the temperature profile, calculated for a particular cure schedule, is used to gauge the progress of the optimization. The optimum schedule is the one which minimizes the error.

The results of the optimization are given in Figure 5. As can be seen the part temperature is virtually identical to the target temperature. The autoclave temperature looks like the mirror image of the part temperature in Figure 2.

CONCLUSIONS

Optimum cure schedules that minimize heatup time can be calculated using the optimization scheme outlined here. The heatup time for the laminate studied was reduced to 60 minutes from in excess of 300 minutes.

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Figure 1. Tooling setup.

Figure 2. Temperature history of 128 ply laminate of IM6/3501-6. A comparison of measured and predicted temperatures.

Figure 3. Temperature history of the same laminate as in Figure 2. A comparison of measured and predicted temperatures.

Figure 4. Temperature history of Maguire and Billington's G(MR&D).150 laminate. A comparison of measured and predicted temperatures. (Boeing Commercial Aircraft Company BMY-SR-3952).

Figure 5. Optimum cure schedules for laminate associated with Figures 2 and 3. Autoclave temperature was calculated using the optimization scheme.